

ISic0146

I.Sicily inscription 0146

Language

Latin

Type

funerary

Material

limestone

Object**Editor**

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

Jonathan Prag,James Cummings,James Chartrand,Valeria Vitale,Michael Metcalfe,Tuuli Ahlholm,Simona Stoyanova

Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Thermae Himeraeae

Place of origin (modern)

Termini Imerese

Provenance**Coordinates****Current Location**

Italy, Sicily, Termini Imerese, Museo Civico

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

1. P(ublio) · Cestio · Catullo

2. ann(orum) · ◻ XXVII

3. et · P(ublio) · Cestio · Catullo

4. patri

Apparatus

Text of ILTermini

There is no immediately clear answer as to what the sign "◻", a reverse C, symbolises here; cf. ISicily0163, CIL 6.15139 (Rome) for analogous use, as pointed out by Bivona (1994). Understanding ◻ as deriving from 'circiter' is one attractive interpretation.

Translation (en)

To Publius Cestius Catullus, [almost?] 27 years of age, and his father Publius Cestius Catullus.

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 284847

EDR 111026

EDCS 22100086

Bibliography

Mommsen, Th. 1883. *Inscriptiones Bruttiorum Lucaniae Campaniae Siciliae Sardiniae Latinae. Pars posterior. Inscriptiones Siciliae et Sardiniae. Corpus Inscriptionum Latinarum, consilio et auctoritate Academiae Litterarum Regiae Borussicae editum.* Berlin. At 10.7385 (<http://arachne.uni-koeln.de/item/buchseite/650798>)

Bivona, L. 1994. *Iscrizioni latine lapidarie del museo civico di Termini Imerese. Kokalos Supplementi / Sikelika serie storica.* Palermo / Rome. At 65

Licensed under a Creative
Commons-Attribution 4.0 licence.

Cite as:

J. Prag et al. (2020-12-17): ISic0146. <http://sicily.classics.ox.ac.uk>. (Collection: TEI edition). <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4334297>